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EDUCATIONAL GAMES USED IN 1ST-2ND GRADE NATIVE LANGUAGE
LESSONS, THEIR CONTENT, EFFECTIVENESS AND METHODOLOG

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Annotation: In this article, educational games used in 1st-2nd grade mother tongue lessons, their content, effectiveness and methodology are analyzed based on specific sources.

Key words: Composition, child, environment, environment, natural phenomena, landscapes, objects, plants, animal world, etc. Introduction: It is known that the game occupies the main place in the activity of a child who is admitted to the 1st grade and takes the first step on the threshold of school. The game is their favorite activity, and they try to combine any activity with the game. Therefore, the teacher allows to increase the effectiveness of the educational process by using it in accordance with the purpose, without squeezing their favorite activity - the game. Play is an integral part of a child's life. Through the game, the child gets to know the environment, natural phenomena, landscapes, objects, plants, animals. Didactic games are of particular importance in the organization of mental and physical activity of students during primary education. Literature review: Literacy teaching is a very important responsibility and at the same time it is an honorable period that will remain in the student's memory for a lifetime. depends on the level of development of skills. That's why special attention is paid to literacy training in educating young people and preparing them for life. In order to master the pronunciation and writing of each sound-letter perfectly, it depends on the formation of independent thinking and creative work skills in the student. Grammatical games used during literacy training encourage students to use their full potential and pay special attention to the subtleties of each sound and letter. Grammatical games used in this period are diverse and provide the student with knowledge, prevent him from getting bored, and create an opportunity to enjoy the work he has done. It is possible to achieve effective results if teaching children of the 1st grade is based on the game. In order not to bore children of this age, to organize reading and writing lessons in an interesting way, to read well, to form and strengthen the skills of writing, it is necessary to properly organize and organize writing lessons in the form of a game. When organizing grammar games with students, it is necessary to involve more students who make mistakes and shortcomings in correct and beautiful writing. When choosing the type of grammar game

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used during literacy training, it is necessary to take into account the characteristics, interests and capabilities of the students. Advanced primary school teachers working in the schools of our country have created many didactic games for use in the process of teaching literacy to first graders. They are achieving good results using them in the course of the lesson. 1 Elementary school students learn a number of phonetics. Vowels and consonants are distinguished based on pronunciation and comparison. They will get practical knowledge about voiced and unvoiced pronunciation of consonants, paired and unpaired voiced and unvoiced consonants. In this regard, the testing method used in elementary grades allows to understand whether sounds are voiced or voiceless. This, in turn, helps in writing correctly. Also, in these classes, he gets practical knowledge about syllables and their types, stressed and unstressed syllables, and the effect of sounds on each other. Mastering all this creates a number of complications. Because of this, it is useful to use didactic games related to phonetics in primary classes. "Word making" game. The game is played during literacy training. Playing these games allows students to fully understand the importance of sound in word formation. As students participate in this game, the formation of words in different ways arouses great interest. They can directly enjoy the new words they have created. The word formation game is performed on the basis of the content-editing (analytical-synthetic) sound method of literacy education. The second part of this method means to create, build, combine. The word formation game is created by adding different sounds and syllables to the word. This game creates new words by adding sounds to words in different ways. A game of creating a new word by adding one sound to the beginning of the word. Based on the requirement of this game, the student creates a new word by adding a sound from the beginning of a given word. A new word is formed by adding a vowel before a word that starts with a consonant or by adding a consonant before a word that starts with a vowel. Son - o +son o'lka- y o'lka ola - lola ota -bota - nota ayiq- qayiq or- bor - tor o'roq - s o'roq osh - qosh- mosh . In this game, you can make a single word by adding sounds to some words (numbereasy), and you can make a series of words from some words. The game can be played both with the whole class and in the form of a competition formed by groups of students. "Create a new word by adding letters to the end of the word" game. The procedure of the game is almost the same as word building games. Wordforming suffixes expressed by one letter are also involved in the formation of such words. If this game is played during literacy training, it is not required to provide information about word-forming additions. In this period, students do not have knowledge about word structure and word formation. Because primary school students learn their mother tongue more practically. The skills developed during this

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period are studied as formative additions after learning the structure of words in the next grades. Before starting the game, the teacher explains the order of the game through one or two examples. Aziz –Aziza tog‘- tog‘a sayla – saylov Nur - nura, yelka - yelkan xol-xola olti -oltin varaq – varaqa ot- ota tol- tola k o‘z –k o‘za ola -olam Students of the class are divided into two groups and the notebook is divided into the same number of parts. Each group writes the word they found on the corresponding part of the board. The group with the most words is the winner. The game can be played with the whole class. After a certain time, the game ends. The student who finds the most words is the winner and is encouraged. A game to create a new word by adding letters in the middle of the word. One type of word building game is to add a letter to the middle of a word to form a new word. The game is often played with two-syllable words. A new word is formed by adding a consonant to the middle of a two-syllable word. This game improves the intelligence of students. Understands the difference in meaning of the words in the Uzbek language lexicon. The student's vocabulary increases. Full volitional attention is used to fulfill the game condition. Before starting the game, the teacher explains one or two words on the board. sara - sayra , zira - ziyrak During the game, students can find the following words. Tana– ko‘mak –ko‘lmak qatiq- qattiq qara- qayra mashoq- mashshoq ula - ushla pila - pilla tola -toshla sila – siyla

SUMMARY: This game is similar to the game of creating a new word by adding a sound to the beginning of the word. It increases children's activity and sharpens their minds. It can be conducted with the participation of all students, or between rows of desks. The teacher determines how many words should be found for each syllable

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